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DELIVERABLE REPORT

WP18 Bridging Academia to industry

D18.4

Mid term report on Outreach, Awareness and engagement to industrial community

Due date

- - -

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DELIVERABLE TITLE

Mid term report on outreach, awareness and engagement to industrial community

DELIVERABLE DESCRIPTION

This report is a deliverable of Task 18.2 dedicated to the outreach to industrial community as part of WP18 "Bridging academic and industrial research". This report proposes a follow up of the activities that have been carried out in the framework of WP from M19 to M36. It follows a marketing and dissemination campaign that has started in April 2022, just after the outreach strategy report (D18.2) have been issued at M13 and the publication of the first outreach report at M36. It also follows This report includes the main objectives of the outreach activities, the activities that have been implemented so far and some guidelines about how to improve the future campaign and foster innovation.

It will cover the different topics:

- THE CONTEXT, OBJECTIVES, CURRENT KPI AND THE ONGOING MARKETING STRATEGY
- THE FOLLOW UP ABOUT MARKETING, OUTREACH AND DISSEMINATION

- GOOD PRACTISES AND NEXT STEPS FOR UPGRADED OUTREACH CAMPAIGN

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NATURE

- R – Report
- P – Prototype
- DEC - Websites, Patent filing, Press & media actions, Videos, etc.
- O - Other

DISSEMINATION LEVEL

- P - Public
- PP - Restricted to other programme participants & EC: (Specify)
- RE - Restricted to a group (Specify)
- CO - Confidential, only for members of the consortium

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1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report is a deliverable of Task 18.2 dedicated to the outreach to industrial community as part of WP18 "Bridging academic and industrial research". This report proposes a follow up of the activities that have been carried out in the framework of WP from M19 to M36. It reports on the marketing and dissemination campaign that has in April 2022, just after the outreach strategy report (D18.2). This report includes the main objectives of the outreach activities, the activities that have been implemented so far and some guidelines about how to improve the future campaign and foster innovation.

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2 PREMISES

2.1 Context

The main goal of NFFA-Europe-Pilot (NEP) is to foster innovation and enhance European competitiveness in nanoscience and nano-to-micro analysis and nanotechnology. The uniqueness of NEP is to offer, to a broad academic user community and to industry/SMEs, combined access to state-of-the-art tools in nanoscience and nano-to-micro analysis available in Europe. The PILOT project builds on the success of the NFFA-Europe INFRAIA-1-2014-2015 action. During the NFFA-Europe project (2015 - 2021) there have been 15 calls, 321 proposal were accepted and the number of accepted industrial proposal has reached 11.5%. This number is higher than the objective initially set which was 5%. The rate of acceptance was 65%. For NEP campaign, 16 quarterly calls are scheduled along 5 years (accounting for the access deferral periods needed at the beginning and at the end of the project). For the first period (M1-M18), 122 proposals have been submitted, 14 of them involved industry, which represents 11% of all the research projects submitted. This number is higher with the objective of 7% which is a good sign of attractiveness of NFFA research infrastructure to the industry. 3 Proposals only were submitted directly via SMEs which corresponds to only 2% of all proposals.

2.2 Objectives

NEP has raised its ambition compared to NFFA-Europe by raising the objective of accepted proposals with industry involvement to 7%. The estimated number of projects over the 5 years is 420. According to the outreach strategy report (D18.2), to fulfill the 7% industry engagement, the estimated number of industrial projects accepted has to be 32 and the estimated number of submitted proposals has to be at least 49 with a rate of acceptance of 65% (NFFA-Europe). It means, at least 3 industrial proposals have to be submitted at each call or 12 by year (4 calls). The marketing and dissemination plan have been established in compliance with this KPI. Furthermore, the number

of proposal submitted directly by companies is also monitored, with the ambition to reach at least 5% (it was 2% for the first period).

2.3 Industry involvement

In total, for the first 10 calls, 355 proposals have been submitted via the peer-review access. 40 of them are involved with industry which represents 11.3% of all the research projects submitted. This number is higher with the objective of 7% which is a good sign of attractiveness of NFFA research infrastructure to the industry. 22 proposals have been submitted directly from SMEs which corresponds to 6.2% of all proposals.

This KPI is satisfactory, however we will do our best to improve it, by increasing the proportion of proposals coming directly from companies, in particular SMEs. Developing a high impact network and raise awareness could help in engaging with these potential industrial PIs.

Looking at the evolution over the different calls, Figure 1 shows that it is difficult to identify a clear trend in the number of industrial proposals along the different calls. The total number seems slightly decreasing, while the number of proposals directly solicited by SME is increasing.

The overall proposal acceptance for industry in NEP approaches today an average value of 58%, a bit lower than the average 63% that was registered in the previous NFFA Europe proposal.

Figure 1: Evolution of the industrial proposal along the first 10 calls

Type of industrial involvement

Figure 2: Distribution across the different categories of industrial access.

2.4 Outreach strategy

The outreach strategy has been defined on the deliverable D18.2.

Audience

- SMEs
- Large companies
- PPPs
- Technological clusters
- Potential partners

Communication channels

- Website articles
- Email marketing
- Social networks
- YouTube

Offline marketing

- Business events attendance
- B2B meetings

Supporting materials

- Roll up
- Posters
- Flyers
- Business card
- Leaflets
- PowerPoint presentation

3 DISSEMINATION

3.1 Marketing campaign

Supporting materials

In close collaboration with Promoscience, a rollup has been designed to fit with the expectations of industrials.

- The upper section is dedicated to the main market sectors or the 6 installations where NFFA could be relevant to apply for an industrial.
- A clear message: "free access for industry" has been displayed to attract the potential industrial users.
- The 4 steps process has been shown in a way that is easy to understand and is not scary for the future user.
- The European map locating the partners is displayed on the bottom

Figure 3: rollup for industry (by sectors)

Figure 4: rollup for industry (by Installations)

PowerPoint Presentation

The PowerPoint presentation provided by Promoscience has been updated to better fit the need of industrials. It is structured as followed:

1. Presentation of NFFA-Europe / NEP
2. Case studies/market segmentation
3. Portfolio of techniques
4. Easy 4 step process

LinkedIn campaign

A LinkedIn campaign has been set up in close collaboration with Promoscience to provide a smooth editorial line well balanced between the two communities: academics and industry.

We published:

- 8 posts about case studies
- 4 posts about outreach events

Here are the following pictures that were used and were designed by the NFFA business developer in collaboration with Promoscience.

Figure 5: LinkedIn post @ Nordic Innovation Fair, Figure 6: LinkedIn post @ RDV Carnot,

Figure 7: LinkedIn post @ TechInnov, Figure 8: LinkedIn post @ EuroNanoForum

	<p>FREE-OF-CHARGE ACCESS FOR INDUSTRY</p> <p>nffa.eu research infrastructure</p>		<p>FREE-OF-CHARGE ACCESS FOR INDUSTRY</p> <p>nffa.eu research infrastructure</p>
<p>Case Study: Materials for Renewable energy</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Solar power • Hydrogen technologies • Next generation batteries • Wind energy 	<p>Possible workflow:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pulsed Laser Deposition • X-Ray Diffraction • X-Ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy • Transmission Electron Microscopy 	<p>Case Study: Advanced surface</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Corrosion protection • Smart multi-materials system • Water purification • Air purification 	<p>Possible workflow:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Thixotropy • Flash Lamp Annealing • Cluster Beam Deposition • Scanning Electron Microscopy

Figure 9: LinkedIn post - Materials for renewable energy, Figure 10: LinkedIn post - advanced surface

	<p>FREE-OF-CHARGE ACCESS FOR INDUSTRY</p> <p>nffa.eu research infrastructure</p>		<p>FREE-OF-CHARGE ACCESS FOR INDUSTRY</p> <p>nffa.eu research infrastructure</p>
<p>Case Study: Carbon Credit</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Materials for carbon farming • Materials for carbon capture • Materials for carbon storage 	<p>Possible workflow:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Extreme Ultra Violet Interference Lithography • Secondary Ion Mass Spectrometry 	<p>Case Study: Alternative Active Ingredients</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sustainable fluorescent brightening agents • Sustainable alternatives for AGP • Sustainable chelating agents • Sustainable active chemicals 	<p>Possible workflow:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Thixotropy • Flash Lamp Annealing • Cluster Beam Deposition • Scanning Electron Microscopy

Figure 11: LinkedIn post – carbon credit, Figure 12: LinkedIn post – Alternative active ingredients

Regularly, new contacts with strategic entities are made through LinkedIn and a private message is sent to invite them for a discussion about micro- and nanotechnologies with the aim to raise awareness by organizing a B2B meeting to introduce the distributed research infrastructure.

Email marketing

Regularly, email marketing is sent to valuable contacts that could be interested about submitting a proposal. The type of companies targeted are SMEs. For the contacts, we aim at CEO, CTO or sustainability & innovation managers.

Around 50 email marketing have been sent to innovative SMEs in micro- & -nanotechnologies in the domain of solar energy and nanoelectronics. 6 B2B meetings have been scheduled to raise awareness about NFFA-Europe.

A work has been done to design an impactful corporate email banner and email signature.

The picture on the signature is changed accordingly with the sector of market of the contact to reach.

Figure 13: email banner

New industry section in the NFFA website

An updated industry section has been included in the NFFA website. This section would provide specific information useful to industrial applicants and in particular some details on the access and the possibility to have dedicated advices.

Figure 14: industry webpage on the NFFA website

3.2 Events attendance

The following events has been attended:

1. Nordic Innovation Fair, 26th-27th 2022 of September, Copenhagen
2. Micronora, 27th-30th of September 2022, Besançon, France
3. RDV Carnot, 12th – 13th of October 2022, Paris
4. 10th Symposium of NIA, 23rd of November 2022, Brussels
5. TechInnov, 28th – 29th of March 2023, Paris
6. Journée Technique Nanomatériaux, 10th of May 2023, Paris
7. ITF World, 16th – 17th of May 2023, Antwerp, Belgium
8. EuroNanoForum, 11th – 13th of June, Lund, Sweden
9. Leti Innovation Days, 27th – 29th of June, Grenoble, France

3.5 Business meetings campaign

- During and following the attended events **90 B2B meetings** have been organized, mainly with technological clusters, spinoffs and large companies.
- Following the email marketing campaign **10 B2B meetings** have been organized.
- Finally, **5 B2B meetings** have been organized thanks to the LinkedIn campaign.
- In total, **105 B2B meetings** have been organized during the period April – July 2023.

As most of the meetings are organized with SMEs, a specific focus is made on incentives like the free-of-charge peer-review access, the confidentiality of the access and the technical consultancy. Following these meetings, a reference contact have been identified to pursue the discussion. The discussion focused mainly on their interest to submit a proposal, or to join the consortium by applying to the next call for new providers or to act as multiplier and spread the information about the NFFA research infrastructure. In total, 6 have shown interest in submitting and a discussion have started. In total, 5 companies are interested in joining the consortium by applying to the next call for new providers.

3.6 ICONet

Among the NEP project, ICONet is a pilot network of the industrial and commercial officers (ICOs) of the providers (ICONet) as an ad-hoc solution for facilitating industrial and SME access. Such a network is already in place and most of the member facilities indicated a reference person. The main goal of the ICONet is to provide a dedicated intermediation service, which will exploit, coordinate and rationalize the competence available in the different Industrial Contact Offices often already present at member facilities. This ICOs network (ICONet) contributes to understand and translate the needs expressed by the industrial user and identifying the most appropriate technique to answer the need. Furthermore, the ICONet accompany the industrial users for the access preparation and, when relevant, help to identify academic partners, among the NFFA user community, to collaborate with, if this can be helpful to make the proposal even stronger.

A kick off meetings has been called with the ICONet where the marketing strategy has been presented and validated. During this meeting, it has been emphasised as large companies are mainly

interested in proprietary access. In this respect, the ICONet can act as a first entry point for the whole consortium.

3.7 Industrial Advisory Board

In 2021 NEP run a call for industrial partners that ended with the association of the company ELEN as a consortium partner and leader of Task 18.3.

This call for partners was relatively successful with almost 20 applicants, mainly SMEs and intermediary companies. With the ambition of valorising and leveraging on such an expression of interest, it was proposed to invite the applicants to take part to an Industrial Advisory Board (IAB). The objective of this board would be to support the WP18 team with:

- Identify interesting networking initiatives (Organization of online/on site events)
- Suggest relevant research topics that could be of interest for industry
- Advise on potential strategies to help better bridging the NFFA academic community with industry
- Act as NFFA ambassadors within the nanotechnology and nanomaterial industrial community
- Sharing good practices to help WP18

Eight relevant companies in the sector expressed interest in participating in the IAB.

A first meeting was held on the 28/02/2023. This meeting treated of the missions of the IAB, of the call for new providers and finally of the dissemination activities of NFFA toward the industrial community. In particular, it was discussed the possible organisation of an NFFA industrial final event, and in case the format that this event should have, the contents, the target audience and the potential organisation partners.

3.8 Further initiatives toward SMEs

Considering the importance represented by the SMEs as a target group of NFFA, a set of selected actions has been completed in order to improve their engagement.

Actions in collaboration with the European Innovation Council (EIC)

Considering its great involvement and investment in high-risk projects often involving SMEs, the EIC has been identified as a potential strategic partner, to engage with this important access group. In this respect two initiative has been taken:

- *Dedicated outreach action toward nanotech related SME beneficiaries of EIC grants:* leveraging on the intermediary of Emmanuel Stratakis (Forth - JA manager in NEP – EIC Ambassador for Greece) we had the opportunity to get in touch with Francesco Matteucci, EIC Programme manager who accepted to be our intermediary toward a selection of nanotech focused SMEs with the objective to organise a set of targeted meeting. This initiative is still on-going.

- *Participation to the EIC ecosystem partnership*: this partnership programme was setup by the EIC in order to select a series of potential partners that would have the potential to support the technical programme of their beneficiaries and simplify their collaboration pathways; the application of NFFA was very well received, but unfortunately, it was not eligible because the proposal needed to refer to a proper legal entity and not to a consortium.

Collaboration with the MIXN network (Mediators connecting Industry to X-rays and Neutrons)

In the context of the actions of the ICONet and leveraging on the activities of Uwe Sassenberg (DESY – ICONet leader), in March 2023, Anthony Leonard had the opportunity to present NFFA to the MIXN network (mixn.org). This network is formed by a group of mediator companies acting as industry's bridge to optimise the use of x-rays and neutrons. MIXN serves both small and large industry customers and partners within sectors as diverse as pharmaceuticals, energy, and engineering. Their mission is to work with advanced large-scale research infrastructures across Europe, such as synchrotron and neutron facilities, with the ambition to enable a wide industrial use and exploitation of modern techniques for material analysis and other scientific services.

This action did not have any immediate follow up, but present an great potential for future engagement of industry with NFFA.

4 NEXT STEPS

4.1 Recruitment of a business development

The whole activity of WP18 was orchestrated by Anthony Leonard, a business developer hired at the ESRF and dedicating to NEP 2/3 of his time. Anthony was hired in January 2022 on a 3 years contract. Unfortunately, Anthony departed prematurely from his contract in July 2023. Since then the ESRF has not been able to reopen the position. All the activities have been taken *ad-interim* by Ennio Capria, Deputy Head of Business Development at the ESRF and WP18 leader. Ennio assured the continuity of the activities in the WP, but the volume of activity was reduced to a minimum. This reduction of the promotional activities toward industry, could be considered as the main cause for a reduction of the amount of industrial users applying for NFFA in the last 2 calls.

The opening of a position for another business developer at the ESRF, on a 36 months long contract, is imminent. This resource will be co-funded by various initiatives, among which RIANA, a recently funded INFRAIA-03-2020 project. This configuration will guarantee an absolute synergy and coordination between the industrial engagement activities of the two projects.

4.2 Marketing campaign

To improve NFFA action toward industry, some activities need to be implemented or to be continued. Below here, is the list of actions considered as important to keep track to go forward:

- Send an email to previous industrial users to organize B2B meetings
- Continue the LinkedIn campaign with one post per month
- Continue the email marketing campaign and event attendance with the objective of at least 10 B2B meetings scheduled by month.
- Identify a list of relevant industrial events and support an active participation of the ICONet to maintain and grow the NFFA visibility in the community.

4.3 Industrial Advisory Board

In order to proper follow up with the IAB activities, a proper officialization of this working group has to be made, with the implementation of the following actions:

- Make official the IAB with an invitation email from Dr. Giorgio Rossi, NEP Coordinator
- Create a list email nep-iab@lists.nffa.eu
- Keep the IAB members informed about important industrial outreach actions (led by WP18) so that they would have the opportunity to formulate suggestions, comments
- Sharing with the IAB members the supporting marketing materials so that they may promote NFFA with their local contacts
- Give IAB committee and their members some visibility on the NEP industrial webpage with pictures, bios, Company logos and objectives, missions of IAB.

